

Fermi matrices

Adolf Cusmariu

adolcus@gmail.com

Fermi's seminal article on beta decay **[1]** offers opportunities to recast some expressions in matrix format, connecting such with Pauli and Dirac matrices **[2]**.

1. The matrices

Introduce the following arrays:

$$F_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad F_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad F_3 = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad F_4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad F_5 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

In terms of the functional four-vectors

$$\Phi = (\phi_1, \phi_2, \phi_3, \phi_4) \quad , \quad \Psi = (\psi_1, \psi_2, \psi_3, \psi_4)$$

eqs. (11), p.1153 in **[1]** may now be rendered simply as

$$A_j = \Psi F_j \Phi^{\text{tr}} \quad j = 1, 2, 3, 4$$

using a slight indexing change.

2. Connections

Recall the Pauli σ -matrices (and the 2x2 identity):

$$\sigma_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_2 = i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad \sigma_3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad I_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The Fermi matrices connect to Pauli's set - in block diagonal and/or Kronecker product \otimes form:

$$\begin{aligned} F_1 &= -i \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -\sigma_2 \end{pmatrix} & F_2 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \sigma_3 \\ -\sigma_3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & F_3 &= i \begin{pmatrix} 0 & I_2 \\ -I_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & F_4 &= \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -\sigma_1 \\ \sigma_1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} & F_5 &= \begin{pmatrix} I_2 & 0 \\ 0 & -I_2 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= -i\sigma_3 \otimes \sigma_2 & &= i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_3 & &= -\sigma_2 \otimes I_2 & &= -i\sigma_2 \otimes \sigma_1 & &= \sigma_3 \otimes I_2 \end{aligned}$$

Note that F_5 is also Dirac's γ_0 matrix **[2]**.

3. Products

Like the Pauli matrices, the Fermi set is traceless and of unit determinant; however, not all are involutions:

$$F_1^2 = -\mathbf{I}_4 \quad F_2^2 = -\mathbf{I}_4 \quad F_3^2 = \mathbf{I}_4 \quad F_4^2 = -\mathbf{I}_4 \quad F_5^2 = \mathbf{I}_4$$

where \mathbf{I}_4 is the 4x4 identity matrix; the full Cayley table is shown below.

	F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4	F_5
F_1	$-\mathbf{I}_4$	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1$	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2$	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3$	$-i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2$
F_2	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1$	$-\mathbf{I}_4$	$-i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3$	$i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2$	$-\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3$
F_3	$-\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_2$	$-i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_3$	\mathbf{I}_4	$i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1$	$-i \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2$
F_4	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3$	$-i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2$	$i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1$	$-\mathbf{I}_4$	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1$
F_5	$-i \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_2$	$\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_3$	$i \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2$	$-\sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1$	\mathbf{I}_4

While distinct Fermi matrices are pairwise Hadamard-orthogonal, in the sense that

$$F_j \circ F_k = \mathbf{O}_4 \quad j \neq k$$

where \circ signifies Hadamard product and \mathbf{O}_4 is the 4x4 zero matrix, individual matrices do satisfy:

$$F_1 \circ F_1 = \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad F_2 \circ F_2 = \sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \quad F_3 \circ F_3 = -\sigma_1 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2 \quad F_4 \circ F_4 = \sigma_1 \otimes \sigma_1 \quad F_5 \circ F_5 = \mathbf{I}_2 \otimes \mathbf{I}_2$$

and the self-Hadamard products are involutive:

$$(F_j \circ F_j)^2 = \mathbf{I}_4 \quad j=1,\dots,5$$

[1] F. L. Wilson, 'Fermi's Theory of Beta Decay' Am. J. Phys. 36, #12, Dec. 1968, pp. 1150-1160.

[2] A. Cusmariu, 'From Pauli to Dirac via Kronecker and beyond', Zenodo.org/8023850, June 2023